

Emotions in Design through Materials: An Expressive-Sensorial Atlas as a Project Tool for Design of Materials

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is to construct the theoretical bases as implementation of project instrument that can improve the culture of industrial design and that can help to interpret and to define the complex picture of the phenomenological and perceptive aspects of materials. The exploration of sensorial fields requires proper communication and language tools to manage this relevant dimension of design.

In the contemporary context it's clear the necessity to deepen the parameters of expressiveness and the perception sensorial factors of materials with the purpose to come out the existing relationships with the evocative and emotional sphere of the consumer.

We believe that the better way to reach the objective is to design an instrument to support expressive, sensorial and sensitive methodological approach to materials used in the project. The expressive and sensorial atlas is a useful tool to understand the personal methodology to select materials proper to the trial of project.

Evidently, the choice of correct material for each project doesn't have only to answer to technical, functional, ergonomic demands. It has also to entirely satisfy sensorial, emotional and expressive dimension, to be able to realize the implicit agreeability in the design concept.

Keywords: Materials, expressive-sensorial dimension, the design of materials, emotions

Introduction

The aim of this research is to study the modalities according to which the materials employed in the design stimulate emotions in consumer that enters in their sphere of relationship. Apart from the typology of possible emotions, we will illustrate the development of a tool that can help the designer in managing and creating emotions on the basis of the effects and meanings that can be attributed to the objects, originating from the materials of which they are made.

The emotion and the object

We live in a world full of objects. We use objects to do all activities, and all our experience is mediated by the presence and the use of objects. What else could be the utility of these objects if not to be instruments for our happiness?

In the definition of "emotion", it is possible to find the connection with the material world of the objects. According to Desmet,

Emotions are most relevant for product experience because only they imply a one-to one relationship between the affective state and a particular object: one is afraid of something, angry at someone, happy about something, and so on. The other affective states, such as feelings and moods, do not involve a specific object. Emotions are intentional because they imply and involve a relation between the person experiencing them and a particular object. In addition, people are usually able to identify the object of their emotion (Desmet, 2002).

Therefore, the emotion implies that the object, which stimulates it, gets in contact with the subject that feels it.

But, what is an emotion?

An emotion is a psychic state and a momentary affective state, based on the reaction to perceptions or representations that upset the equilibrium of the organism. The emotional process is stimulated by the surrounding world and therefore it depends, in wide measure, on the sensorial perception; our senses and our perceptive ability allow us to feel emotions.

Therefore, emotions are reactions to external stimuli that can be felt, perceived and elaborated. On this basis, emotion can be defined as the reaction to a stimulation, as the result of a perception and, then, as an output of a process of evaluation.

The process of emotion is explained by the process of appraisal, is the heart of every emotion. Without appraisal there can be no emotion; for all emotions are initiated by an individual's appraisal of his or her circumstances.

Emotions allow us to locate ourselves in our surroundings and choose situations, lifestyles and, why not, even the daily objects that we want around us. Emotions are subjective. Therefore, they have a precise duration, a determined time of manifestation; and one can experience more than one type of emotion at the same time. Since emotions are subjective it is difficult to evaluate them. Moreover, emotions are strongly conditioned by individual, cultural and social factors.

Emotion through materials

From this point of view, the artefacts that surround us can be considered as a primary source of sensorial and emotional stimulation. One could say that a product has two components that act as stimuli and provoke emotional reactions: its form and the material of which it is made.

There are different types of emotions provoked by objects. We would like to focus our attention on the emotions elicited by product appearance. What else characterizes the appearance of the objects more, if not the materials of which they are constituted?

...the material object is the object that presents itself to us into the field of the perception experience, the kind of experience that is brought to us by our senses. The material object, the piece of matter is the one that resists the touch, that prevents the sight, or that can be noticed because of its odour, adding the fact that the idea, the representation, get involved into a different kind of experience... (Macé, 1998).

It is not easy to separate the idea of form from the idea of matter that composes it, because, especially in philosophical terms, the form has long been defined as something to impose to the subject, “...*la forme est une manière de décrire les transformations purement matérielles.*” (...shape is the way to describe purely material transformations) (Macé, 1998).

Material realizes a shape. The same material could embody a different shape and, therefore, would not be perceived in the same way. The same shape realized with different materials recalls to other sensorial perceptions and to further emotions. The material is the interface of the object. The interface is the place in which communication and therefore message subsist, for definition. Objects also communicate through their material interface that has to be designed considering their great evocative and emotional potentialities. Design always means to manipulate sensorial data. Since the aim of this research is to relate emotions and materials, we will focus on the possibility of creating a useful design tool, of managing the complexity of sensorial stimuli and governing the project from the emotional aspect of the personality of the product. "Product designer seek to blend the technical with the aesthetic, combining practical utility with emotional delight." (Ashby and Johnson, 2003)

The expressive-sensorial characterization of materials and their surfaces is the theme of the research presented here.

“The materials from which a product is fabricated can play a major role in determining how pleasurable – or displeasurable – a product is for those experiencing it.” (Jordan, 2002) In any production experience it is obvious that materials for design are chosen in terms of their properties, safety, functionality and efficiency. The expressive power and character of the designed objects can be determined through the use and selection of materials. Therefore it becomes very important to emphasize the need to invest not only in the formal aspect of objects but also in the selection of materials. The materials have a fundamental role in expressive, evocative and symbolic functions in the human emotional mechanisms.

The expressive-sensorial characterization of materials

The research on materials as the carrier of emotions becomes concrete in the project of an “expressive-sensorial” Atlas. The atlas is a useful tool, first of all, to the education of designers. As I said previously, one needs a project tool that can contribute to the industrial design’s culture, and which can help in the interpretation of the complex framework of the phenomenological, perceptive and sensorial aspects of the materials and their surfaces.

The purpose is to furnish a tool which:

- relates to sensorial, and therefore expressive characterization of the materials used in the project,

- makes the designer aware not only of the existence of an expressive dimension of the materials, but that also gives him a basic idea of how to manage and check the parameters that govern the materials.

This tool is aimed at designers who are sensitive to the problem and the expressive and phenomenological dimension of the materials.

Arranging the information as an atlas, that is a collection of illustrated tables, should be stimulating as a means of communication of this research, considering, above all, that it has a systematic and not hierarchic organization (the criteria of order of knowledge within an organic complex).

The term atlas is defined in the encyclopedia as “a systematic collection of geographic charts

for consultation or study, featuring the entire surface of the Earth or part thereof in different scales”. Furthermore, the existence of thematic atlases is envisaged. These are defined as “systematic collections of charts which represent the spatial distribution of a fact or phenomenon, whatever it may be”. Therefore, the definition can be extended to cover all collections of large-scale illustrated tables.

The structure of the atlas

The methodology that has allowed the development of the atlas is based, first of all, on the theoretical definition of the fundamental parameters for the expressive-sensorial description of the materials. Then, the parameters are correlated with the intrinsic properties of the materials. The correlation allows underlining as the phenomenical appearance of the materials depends and it can be modified technologically acting on the physical, chemical, mechanics properties of the materials. The correlation between the appearance and properties of the material is recognized as the most important point of the research. To understand and explain what determines a certain effect, and understand how and on what one needs to act to ensure that the effect follows the project’s requirements, is one of the more interesting possibilities for material’s design.

The research develops a general methodology applicable to any class of materials. Deepened studies and punctual could be done considering the single specific classes.

The theoretical part of the atlas is composed from two tool tables: the table of the parameters and the table of the properties, and from the theoretical tables for the exemplification of the qualities of the matter.

The table of parameters

The Table of the Parameters includes and illustrates all those parameters that are considered fundamental for the expressive-sensorial description of the materials. The parameters that have been selected and recorded in this table are those that allow making a phenomenological description of materials independently from their class of affiliation.

The omission of color and its relative chromatic dimension was intentional because it would have taken much in-depth work, taking time to other much less studied aspects. It was a

personal choice not lacking in strong motivations.

The table is structured according to two macro-togetherness that define "the aspect": the tactile aspect and the photometric aspect. For each aspect, we found these parameters significant: Touch and Texture for the tactile aspect and Brightness and Transparency for the photometric aspect. "The parameters" are four and they refer and describe the aspects. The parameters are declined depending on the "attributes of quality". Therefore there are four parameters that refer to and describe the aspects. In turn the parameters are declined according to their "quality attributes"; the indicated qualities are not the only ones possible, but are those fundamental for the job, and are considered suitable for the Atlas project. It is worth noting this to not risk giving a too definitive and universal character to the choices made.

Parameters
to describe aesthetically and sensorially the design's materials

touch	texture	brilliance	transparency
warm/cold soft/hard flowing/stilted light/weighty	smooth uneven	gloss matt	trasparent traslucent opaque

tactil aspect photometryc aspect

Figure 1. The Table of Parameters

The definition of the parameters

The Touch

The touch is defined as a specified sensation that arises in response to stimulation of the tactile receptors.

Tactile sensations are sent from the objects' surfaces, made up from different materials and finishes, to the subject in question. Touch covers both the sensations caused by contact and those caused by moving on the surface. Definite sensations are a result of these different interactions; thermal and compliance feelings are the sensations arising from contact with the

material's surface, whereas the sensations of flowing and weight results from actions of slide and movement.

Touch is the accumulation of sensations sent from the material to the subject in a tactile way. As the truthfulness and existence of a sensation is also given by its contrary, one can use opposition and contrast as arguments. It is the parameter that needs more attributes to describe it.

The physical properties connected with superficial touch are: for hot/cold, the conductivity and thermal capacity; for soft/hard, the hardness and elasticity; for flowing/restraint, the coefficient of friction, elasticity and weakening load; finally for light/heavy, density. One can obtain instrumental measurements of touch by using: the calorimeter, the hardmeter, dynamometer, the tribometer and the pycnometer.

The Texture

Texture is defined as something composed of closely interwoven elements. Texture is an element of tactile characterization of the surfaces, but it is also visible.

The application of a texture, or texturization, involves the alteration of the material's surfaces by marking, raising or engraving them. To simplify matters, one can say that there are smooth and bi-dimensional textures, obtained by applying a design, and engraved and tri-dimensional textures, obtained by deep or shallow incisions.

Texture's effect comes from the interaction of many elements that define a visual pattern by which the texture is organized. With regard to this, it is important to define the scale of observation, rarefaction and accumulation of the elements from which it is made.

In its "expressive-sensorial" characterization, it is the texture's tactile aspect that is of prime interest, or that which one perceives by touch. By choice, we will not go into what is linked to the formality and typology of the texture's design.

The physical property connected to the texturization of surfaces is the roughness. The roughness (unevenness) can be measured and checked with a profilometer.

The Brillancy

Brilliancy is a visual sensation which a human observer experiences when light covers a

surface from which it is reflected, depending on the relative amount of the flow of radiation. It concerns the quantity of the image that is formed by reflection on the surface of a body.

Diffused light degrades the sensation of brilliancy, therefore, gloss refers to a shiny surface, whereas matt is an opaque and highly diffused surface. The choice of the attributes is given by the same definition of a property that describes a material's optical property. The surface finish influences greatly the different sensations of brilliancy that can be obtained. The physical property connected to the brilliancy is the gloss and the haze. "Gloss is the attribute of surfaces that causes them to have a shiny or lustrous appearance. It is generally associated with specular reflection by the surfaces of objects". (Hunter and Harold, 1987) One can obtain instrumental measurements relating to brilliancy by using a glossmeter, or notational empiric measurements using the Gloss Scale NCS.

The Transparency

The aspects of transparency are pertinent to the material's whole body. A body that can be penetrated in its entirety by light radiation, allowing a perfect vision of objects placed on the other side of it, is called transparent. On the contrary, a body that does not transmit light thus losing all information on the objects placed behind it, is called opaque. In the middle of these two extremes is the translucent body, one that transmits light but, at the same time, diffuses it in all directions, causing the objects placed behind it to lose their sharpness.

The attributes of transparency's quality are explained by its definition. These attributes are subtracted from the light's interaction phenomena as illustrated in the material's optical properties.

There are intrinsically transparent materials, others opaque by nature, and still others for which it is possible to plan a degree of transparency.

The transparency is a parameter that can be considered "subtractive", it means that it can be removed but it is not possible to add.

The physical properties connected to the transparency of the materials are the index of refraction, haze, clarity and transmittance. Instrumental measures of the transparency can be obtained using a refractometer.

The table of the properties

One can proceed with the creation of the Table of Properties after a deep analysis of the parameters. The main aim of the Table in question is to show how the material's properties can be linked with the parameters and qualities. These properties are subdivided and arranged according to the "expressive-sensorial" characterization aspects. From this, it is evident that the matter's chemical/physical properties are directly involved in, and useful to, the expressive-sensorial description of the appearance of the materials for design.

Figure 2, Table of Properties

The theoretical tables

After having illustrated the structure of the chosen parameters and their correlated properties, it is time to illustrate the parameters according to their qualitative attributes. To this end, tables were planned and made in which there are examples of the various qualities attributed to the chosen parameter.

The aim of the Theoretic Tables is to illustrate the qualities and, therefore, no one particular class of material was chosen, but different materials will be used in the table's creation in order to point out the differences and help to better understand the concepts.

The tables include concrete examples of the aspect and of the considered parameter, a simple and precise definition of the parameter and the link between the properties and measuring instruments

Figure 3, Example of the Theoretic Table (transparency).

The sensorial profile

Based on the Tool Tables and on the Theoretical Tables, it is possible to create what has been called "sensorial profile" of the considered sample of material.

The sensorial profile can be made on more levels. The first level concerns the individualization of the parameters of expressive-sensorial characterization; directly observing and touching the sample; it can be compiled a description of the sensorial profile of material.

At a second level, information considered are the ones that does not have a possible direct perceptive experience, but they are essential for the sensorial profile or rather the information that could compose the sample's identity card: the material of which is composed, the technical card from which it is possible to go up again to the properties, the technology of workmanship used to obtain the sample, to what other technologies it can be submitted.

The sensorial profile must be completed also with the possibility to find numbers of the related parameter's properties considered interesting for the characterization, and so measurements can be done with suggested instruments.

The aim of making a sensorial profile of sample is to understand if the qualities that we perceive due to the sample, can also be maintained in the possible application, or they are exclusively communicated by that precise sample. This observation is very important, and keeps to the footlight, remarks tightly tied up to form and technologies, that also have a role of primary importance in the expressive-sensorial characterization of material.

However, we decided not to directly deal us with formal and technological matters, it is

necessary to focus ourself on the phenomenology of matter and on the ways materials's selection based on their aspect, or their phenomenological potentialities.

Maps of relationships and differences on the basis of the filed information can be composed realizing the sensorial profile of different samples, operating a preselection of the materials on the basis of the project demands.

The personal realization of the atlas starts in this way, and it shapes itself as a collection of sensorial profiles of different samples among which it is possible to establish of the proximities and of the *lontanazes*, among which to trace some *mappatures*.

Conclusions

In the development of the research, we tried to make coming up the importance of expressive-sensorial characterization of materials for the emotional dimension of the design. What has been valued it concerns an original approach to the materials that in project context must have studied, departing from their aspect and from their image to reach the technical, physical and technological properties.

The creation of an atlas as a tool wants to show that, opportunely studied and deepened, it is realizable a new methodology of relationship with the matter that could find out also interesting developments outside pedagogic context.

Actually, it is not possible to appraise the right and utility of this tool, because of still not adequately developed and tested. Surely we can say that the goal of the research has been to introduce the matter and to start to establish some project lines on which to operate. From the described situation, it's notices that we find ourselves operating in a continuous movement context, and that the materials does not constitute an easily exhaustible matter. In fact, at the end of the present job, we make our deliberations to give certain curious cue to future research on the relationship between emotion and design.

The first deliberation concerns the existing relationships among the various qualities and among the parameters of the characterization. The soft materials "seem" more hot than those hard, the hard materials "seem" heavier than those soft, the gloss material "seem" more braked of those matt, can a material be matt and transparent contemporarily?, and so on.

These relationships exist very often only in the sensorial and perceptive dimension, but surely they can find an explanation also in the relationships that exist among the properties of the material.

A second kind of examination, it could concern the contribution of the technology to the exploitation of the expressive-sensorial dimension of the materials. The goal would be to focus on the workmanship's processes to furnish an useful tool to choice among different technologies to get different effects.

The more granted idea, but perhaps the more easily prosecutable and guarantor of successes, could hypothesize the study of the expressive-sensorial dimension's characterization for every single class of materials. Starting from the analysis of lifetime of particular class, it could be underlined where, as, when and because some modifications can happen and for what parameters of the characterization. This approach would recognize a meaningful involvement to the technologies and would take the responsibility for the total lifetime of the considered material.

Other study could be turned on the parameters of the expressive-sensorial characterization that we have not been volunteering treated. So there would be researches on the color, on the odor and on the sound of the materials.

A last consideration could be turned on the "innovative" materials that some cases could allow today to compose the "tables of impossible materials", where properly the materials would have aspects an semblances that have never been able to have. Expanded metals and soft marbles are only an example of these how much less suggestive materials for the project. And it could still quote more other...

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